

Incorporating Uncertainty in Automated Seismic Interpretation; Geobody Volumetrics

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Introduction

- **ML based seismic interpretation in an exploration context**
- **Uncertainty analysis in deep learning models**
- **Discuss how the additional information provided by machine learning can impact on volume estimates via examples on a well known dataset**

Subsurface Uncertainty

The subsurface is not uncertain.

What is uncertain is our measurements and models of the subsurface.

It is the uncertainty of these that we need to in turn model and work to quantify as well as understanding their accuracy.

Michael Pyrcz @GeostatsGuy · 1d

Embrace #uncertainty! It is not a property of the #subsurface, it's due to our ignorance! Result of sparse data + #heterogeneity! There is no objective uncertainty, it is a model that depends on scale & no matter what you do, don't even think about uncertainty in the uncertainty!

Uncertainty in Deep Learning

Dropout as a Bayesian Approximation:
Representing Model Uncertainty in Deep
Learning. Gal, Ghahramani. 2015 (rev.
2016) [<https://arxiv.org/abs/1506.02142>]

Probabilistic Seismic Facies
Classification. Mosser, Stevenson,
Oliveira. FORCE Seminar 2018
[<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1466917>]

Dropout randomly disables X% of units
in a network during training.

MC Dropout applies 50% dropout at training
and prediction time to approximate a
random process (Bernoulli Distribution)

New Zealand - Taranaki Basin

Thanks to New Zealand GNS for providing the open seismic dataset

Reproduced from [Mattos, Alves & Scully 2018](#)

Lithostratigraphic Unit - Labelling

Lithostratigraphic Predictions

Example labels

Inline Prediction

Crossline Prediction

200 Realisations - Lithostratigraphy

**Predicted lithostratigraphy classes
(orange) clinoform package**

**Frequency (occurrence, voxel-wise)
for clinoform package**

Gully Systems

Potential stratigraphic traps

Complex geomorphology

Varying infill response

Extensive and difficult to pick

The Objective

$$\text{HCIIP} = \text{GRV} \times \text{N/G} \times \text{POR} \times S_{hc} / \text{FVF}$$

HCIIP = hydrocarbons in place*

GRV = gross rock volume

N/G = net / gross ratio

POR = porosity

S_{hc} = hydrocarbon saturation

FVF = formation volume factor

*of oil, solution gas, free gas, condensate and normal surface conditions

Interpretation of
complex geobodies

hard-to-track basal
surfaces

Manual (point)
interpretation in
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takes time and is
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Manual (point) interpretation in traditional software takes time and is prone to errors

Gridding of manual (point) interpretation suffers from picking inconsistency

Gullies Labels

XI4910 - crop

Gullies Prediction

XL 4980

XL 4980

Isolating Potential Trap

(yellow) average across a number
of realisations

Saddle point between N & S feeding

GRV Estimate for Gully

- 250 realisations using Monte Carlo Dropout
- Cropped at Oil/Water contact 1248ms
- Created stacked volume & examined the bounding geobody
- Created a bounding polygon & calculated GSV in this area for all realisations
- (p10=0.360, p90=0.391) Gm3

Training Time: 3 hours

Prediction: 1 min / realisation

HCIIP

=

GRV

*

N/G

*

POR

*

SHC

/

FVF

Deep Learning ASI with Uncertainty

Monte Carlo simulation based on below distributions

ML inversion and/or contextual queries on ML derived N/G logs

ML inversion and/or contextual queries on ML derived POR logs

ML inversion and/or contextual queries on ML derived SHC logs

Contextual queries on analogous field data

Conclusions

- Various approaches to introducing model uncertainty in ML methods (MC Dropout demonstrated here). These type of methods will be prevalent in approaches to ASI.
- This enable us to look a significantly more variation in static models than scenario analysis can achieve
- We will be generating interpretation data with quantification of uncertainty for probabilistic volumetrics
- Generate multiple realisations for flow simulation

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ANALYTICS**